

Anonymising personal data under the data legislative *acquis* established by the Data Governance Act

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Anonymisation
Anonymous data
Data sharing agreement
Data access agreement
Data intermediation service provider

ABSTRACT

The re-identification risk test, established under Recital 26 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), constitutes a milestone in assessing the efficiency of personal data anonymisation. Its interpretation and implementation have been largely discussed by scholars and practitioners. This article illustrates the challenges to the plausibility of the anonymisation risk test, especially considering the most recent European jurisprudence on data anonymisation, and the recent Digital Omnibus proposal. Although this regulatory proposal aims at repealing the Data Governance Act, it transposes its data governance model into the Data Act.

With the aim to foster the regulatory and scholar debate of this new proposal, our work puts forward a new perspective on data anonymisation within the frame the DGA, considering its potential to reduce legal uncertainty to the application of anonymisation through data intermediaries. Specifically, our work investigates how Data Intermediation Service Provider (DISP) could support data holders in anonymising data, impacting on accountability when providing access to data and sharing of data. Although the involvement of DISPs may raise additional questions in terms of the responsibilities of a DISP, this article outlines the pertinent rules established by the DGA to analyse and discuss such potential responsibilities and to elaborate on their possible contractual consequences with respect to data anonymisation.

1. Introduction

The General Data Protection Regulation¹ (hereinafter referred to as GDPR) considers anonymisation as one of the main safeguards - together with pseudonymisation² - for protecting personal data and impacting the (direct or indirect) identifiability of individual data. The increased

amount of shared data, within and outside the Digital Single Market, increased the risk of re-identification,³ challenging the implementation of Recital 26. According to it, to determine whether a natural person is identifiable, account should be taken of “all the means reasonably likely to be used (e.g., such as singling out)” either by the controller or by another person “to identify an individual directly or indirectly”. The

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¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (GDPR). Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

² The difference between anonymisation and pseudonymisation is represented by the ir-/reversibility of the output when transforming personal data to anonymised or pseudonymised data. Anonymisation is generally considered an irreversible process, requiring breaking the link between data subjects and their data (irreversibly). Pseudonymisation, on the other hand, is considered a reversible process, which does not break the link between data subjects and their data, as a pseudonym replaces the personal identifier. This orientation was also recalled on the Data Protection Directive. Lately, there seems to be a shift in argumentation, as the European Court has stressed the need to consider the data recipient’s position to determine the reversibility of the process, impacting the assessment of the nature of data as anonymous.

³ Andrea Gadotti and others, ‘Anonymization: The Imperfect Science of Using Data While Preserving Privacy’ (2024) 10 Science Advances 7053.

Recital goes on to state that, “to ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used, account should be taken of all objective factors”. Although the objective factors mentioned are not enumerated exhaustively, the Recital refers to: “costs” (a), “amount of time required for identification” (b), “available technology at the time of processing” (c) and “technological developments” (d).

Since the GDPR came into force in 2018, this risk test and its assessment have been widely investigated by academics⁴ and data protection authorities (DPAs),⁵ questioning the feasibility of a *zero risk of re-identification (absolute approach)* that appears to be embedded in Recital 26 of GDPR. These investigations have been anchored in the difficulties of avoiding re-identification considering the vast technological developments that challenge the demarcation line between personal and non-personal data.⁶ Scholars⁷, thus, have been deliberating about whether it would ultimately be feasible to implement an *acceptable risk of re-identification (relative approach)*. Following an acceptable risk approach instead of a zero-risk appears more feasible and favourable to data reuses. But beyond that, data anonymisation can still create a misleading perception regarding the actual level of protection and even create a false sense of anonymity in data.

In this regard, the Data Governance Act (DGA)⁸ seemed to offer a new perspective on the matter of anonymisation which could potentially reduce legal uncertainty arising in the context of the anonymisation and the GDPR’s re-identification risk assessment. In fact, the DGA created an organizational framework that complements and supports the establishment of an infrastructure for data processing by setting up data intermediaries, namely Data Intermediation Service Providers (DISPs) and Data Altruism Organisations (DAOs). Particularly, the former seeks to foster commercial relationships, which is where it distinguishes itself from the latter type of data intermediary focusing on altruistic data sharing. DISPs and DAOs will play an essential role in fostering data reuses by providing, among many, data anonymisation services. The intermediary, as a neutral third party, will aid data holders in anonymizing data before unleashing reuses, raising questions in terms of the DISPs responsibilities that encourage the debate on data anonymisation.

⁴ Raphael Gellert, ‘We Have Always Managed Risks in Data Protection Law’: (2016) 2 European Data Protection Law Review 481; Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon and Alison Knight, ‘Anonymous Data v. Personal Data—a False Debate: An EU Perspective on Anonymization, Pseudonymization and Personal Data’ (2017) 34 Wisconsin International Law Journal; Raphaël Gellert, ‘Understanding the Notion of Risk in the General Data Protection Regulation’ (2018) 34 Computer Law and Security Review; S Stalla-Bourdillon, ‘Aggregation, Synthesis and Anonymisation - A Call For A Risk-Based Assessment of Anonymisation Approaches’ in D Hallinan, R Leenes and P De Hert (eds), *Data Protection and Privacy: Data Protection and Artificial Intelligence, CPDP 2021*, vol 13 (Hart Publishing 2021); Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon, ‘A Maturity Spectrum for Data Institutions’ (2021) 19 IEEE Security and Privacy 90; Michele Finck and Asia J Biega, ‘Reviving Purpose Limitation and Data Minimisation in Data-Driven Systems’ [2021] Technology and Regulation 44.

⁵ Emanuela Podda and Francesco Vigna, ‘Anonymization Between Minimization and Erasure: The Perspectives of French and Italian Data Protection Authorities’ in Andrea Kö and others (eds), *Electronic Government and the Information Systems Perspective*, vol 12926 (Springer International Publishing 2021).

⁶ Nadezhda Purtova, ‘The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law’ (2018) 10 Law, Innovation and Technology 40; Michèle Finck and Frank Pallas, ‘They Who Must Not Be Identified—Distinguishing Personal from Non-Personal Data under the GDPR’ (2020) 10 International Data Privacy Law; Nadezhda Purtova, ‘From Knowing by Name to Targeting: The Meaning of Identification under the GDPR’ (2022) 12 International Data Privacy Law 163.

⁷ Ibid., see extensively Section 2 and Section 3.

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act). Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj>

Nevertheless, recently, the European Commission proposed a new Regulation⁹ (aka Digital Omnibus) with the aim to simplify the EU data legislative *acquis* defined as the range of regulatory frameworks and instruments specifically focused and related to data that, currently, creates legal complexity, including some overlaps, as well as not perfectly aligned definitions and questions on the interplay of the regulatory instruments.

The Digital Omnibus proposal has the potential to impact on both, the GDPR and the DGA.

In this regard, this article unfolds the data legislative *acquis* established by the DGA, comprising governance mechanisms, procedures, obligations and duties relating to anonymisation as a condition for lawful and legitimate data reuse, as an additional layer that builds upon the GDPR. To this purpose, the origin of the concept of anonymisation remains grounded in the GDPR.

This article presents doctrinal legal research,¹⁰ also known as black letter or traditional legal research, that exposes rules, principles, and concepts governing a particular area of law. Namely, it focusses on the governance-based regulatory interpretation of anonymisation and identifiability, with the aim to disentangle the relationship between pertinent rules, principles, and concepts to clarify potential ambiguities and offering new perspectives of interpretation at the intersection of law and technology.¹¹ The aim is to shed light on the evolution of the regulatory landscape that harnesses data-driven innovation and that could potentially assist the regulatory and scholar debate initiated by the Digital Omnibus.

Without claiming completeness, this contribution gradually unfolds relevant novelties of the Digital Omnibus proposal, discussing the legal pre-requisites for data anonymisation shaped by the GDPR, and how the EU data legislative *acquis* established by the DGA may enlarge and influence this discussion with the role of the DISPs.

At first, the article will provide an overview of the legal framework for anonymisation as originally conceived in the GDPR, as well as recall the narrative of the Article 29 Working Party’s (i.e., the predecessor of the European Data Protection Board (EDPB)) on the correlation between anonymisation and identifiability, in Section 2. In addition, it shows the evolution in European jurisprudence in current contexts analysed in Court, further bringing to the fore the main features impacting on personal data anonymisation as envisaged by the Digital Omnibus proposal. Afterwards, Section 3 describes the DGA and clarifies how it could assist in overcoming the main discussed features in data anonymisation. In doing so, it discusses the role of neutral intermediaries and describes how they could assist in overcoming the criticalities linked to data anonymisation. Following this line of reasoning, the Section 4 provides suggestions on how to reconcile the most discussed features of anonymisation in relation to intermediary services and potential forthcoming contractual practices. In conclusion, Section 5 offers some considerations on further research directions.

Whilst this article does not claim to resolve potential compliance

⁹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulations (EU) 2016/679, (EU) 2018/1724, (EU) 2018/1725, (EU) 2023/2854 and Directives 2002/58/EC, (EU) 2022/2555 and (EU) 2022/2557 as regards the simplification of the digital legislative framework, and repealing Regulations (EU) 2018/1807, (EU) 2019/1150, (EU) 2022/868, and Directive (EU) 2019/1024 (Digital Omnibus) COM/2025/837 final, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0837>

¹⁰ Mike McConville and Wing Hong (Eric) Chui, *Research Methods for Law* (Edinburgh University Press 2024).

¹¹ Roger Brownsword, ‘Law, Regulation, and Technology: The Bigger Picture of Good Governance’ in Bartosz Brożek, Olia Kanevskaia and Przemysław Pałka (eds), *Research Handbook on Law and Technology* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2023); Olia Kanevskaia and Przemysław Pałka, ‘Introduction to the Research Handbook on Law and Technology’ in Bartosz Brożek, Olia Kanevskaia and Przemysław Pałka (eds), *Research Handbook on Law and Technology* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2023).

issues, it explores data intermediation service's features, considering that intermediaries are evolving organisations¹² which may even differ from sector to sector. Given the current lack of a clear conceptualisation of governance models¹³ resulting from the ongoing development, this article seeks to discuss and contribute to the ongoing discussion with various legal considerations in relation to the access and sharing of anonymous data through data intermediaries.

2. Legal framework on anonymisation

The GDPR frames anonymisation as a data processing operation for protecting personal data, even though it does not provide a concrete definition of it. In its (non-binding) Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques,¹⁴ the Article 29 Working Party (WP29) considers the process of anonymisation as "further processing of data" not compatible with the initial purpose of collection and not integrating a legal basis for processing. According to the advisory work of the WP29, any purpose justifying the collection and use of personal data should be clearly specified;¹⁵ hence anonymisation as such cannot represent, *per se*, a legal basis for collection and processing, except in specific regulated cases (e. g. Art. 89 of the GDPR).¹⁶

The absence of a specific definition of anonymisation seems to be in line with the whole structure of the European legal system where the processing and circulation of data are tied to the *nature*¹⁷ of data, more specifically, to the distinction between personal or non-personal.¹⁸ In this regard, determining whether data is *related to an identified or identifiable natural person* represents the demarcation line between personal and non-personal data.¹⁹

Purtova²⁰ highlights that the GDPR's scope of application focuses mainly on the concept of identifiability and the impact deployed by data

processing techniques on such identifiability. Therefore, the focus of the GDPR is not geared towards the process of anonymisation as such, but rather on its outcome. It thus renders reasonable to frame the concept of identifiability as the demarcation line for the GDPR's scope of application by determining whether the data in question constitutes personal or anonymous data.²¹ The latter is defined, in Recital 26 of the GDPR, as "any information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person" respectively regulated by the Regulation on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the EU (FFDR).

As per Recital 26 of the GDPR, to determine whether a person is identifiable, account should be taken of all the means likely reasonably used, either by the controller or by another person, to identify an individual "directly" or "indirectly". The Recital states further that all objective factors (such as *costs* and amount of *time* required for identification, the *available technology*, and *technological developments*) should be taken into consideration to ascertain whether means are reasonably likely to be used to identify someone. Even though the objective factors are not an exhaustive enumeration, the GDPR thereby leaves a certain margin of appreciation for data controllers and data processors to determine whether data can be considered anonymous. By doing so, the GDPR seems to anticipate minimising the tension when balancing data anonymity and data utility when processing data for unleashing further reuses.

In this regard, the regulatory approach does not recall prescriptive rules on anonymisation,²² mirroring the existing diversity of technical approaches as pictured in Gadotti's review²³ that frames anonymisation as "imperfect science".

This scenario seems to be reflected in the legal community which highlights, from the legal perspective and in terms of reliability, shortcomings and pitfalls of this data processing operation. In fact, legal scholars stressed the decreased reliability of anonymisation, both, in terms of its protection as well as its utility. For instance, before the GDPR came into force, some scholars²⁴ argued that it was not possible to guarantee the irreversibility of anonymisation processes and, at the same time, to maintain the utility of anonymised data, or vice-versa. Others²⁵ highlighted that it is necessary to reach a compromise between the commercial or social value of sharing data and an acceptable re-identification risk, adjusting the data processing to the given scenario.

In the light of the most recent technological developments brought by the data-driven innovation,²⁶ it appears evident that the reliance on a binary approach (reliable/not reliable) that, in fact, reflect the two mutually exclusive definitions of personal and non-personal data, must be overcome. This is mainly because this approach does not consider the

¹² European Commission EU register of data intermediation services, available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-intermediary-services>

¹³ Marina Micheli and others, 'Mapping the Landscape of Data Intermediaries' (Joint Research Centre Publication 2023).

¹⁴ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, 'Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymization Techniques. Adopted on 10 April 2014, WP2016.'

¹⁵ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party, 'Opinion 03/2013 on Purpose Limitation. Adopted on 2 April 2013, WP 203.'

¹⁶ Emanuela Podda, 'Big Data Analysis Systems in IoE Environments for Managing Privacy and Data Protection: Pseudonymity, de-Anonymization and the Right to Be Forgotten' (amsdottorato 2023) <<http://amsdottorato.unibo.it/id/eprint/10697>> accessed 23 September 2025.

¹⁷ Ex art. 4 of the GDPR, personal data is "any information related to an identified or identifiable natural person". Art. 3 of the Free Flow Data Regulation (Regulation EU 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union) mirrors this definition, calling non-personal data as "data other than personal data as defined in article 4.1 of the GDPR".

¹⁸ See extensively Recital 26 GDPR.

¹⁹ The definition of personal data given by the European legal framework is mirroring the concept of PII as defined in the first internationally agreed-upon set of privacy and data protection principles. Namely, recalling the definition of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) as conceived in the main legal sources of the rules on privacy and data protection in Europe: Recommendation of the Council concerning Guidelines Governing the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data, OECD/LEGAL/0188, adopted on 23/09/1980 and amended on 11/07/2013 to address concerns arising from the increased use of personal data and the risk to global economies resulting from restrictions to the flow of information across borders. They represent the first internationally agreed-upon set of privacy principles and have influenced legislation and policy in OECD Member countries and beyond, GDPR included. Moreover, the National Institute of Standard and Technology (NIST) defines PII as "any representation of information that permits the identity of an individual to whom the information applies to be reasonably inferred by either direct or indirect means".

²⁰ Purtova, 'From Knowing by Name to Targeting' (n 6).

²¹ In this sense, Recital 26 highlights that "The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable."

²² Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (n 14).

²³ Gadotti and others (n 3).

²⁴ Helen Nissenbaum, 'The Meaning of Anonymity in an Information Age' (1999) 15 The Information Society 141; Paul Ohm, 'Broken Promises of Privacy: Responding to the Surprising Failure of Anonymization' (2009) 57 UCLA Law Review; Kieron O'Hara, 'Transparent Government, Not Transparent Citizens: A Report on Privacy and Transparency for the Cabinet Office' (2011) A Report on Privacy and Transparency for the Cabinet Office; Stalla-Bourdillon and Knight (n 4).

²⁵ Ann Cavoukian and Khaled El Emam, 'Dispelling the Myths Surrounding De-Identification: Anonymization Remains a Strong Tool for Protecting Privacy' (2011); Sabrina De Capitani di Vimercati and others, 'Data Privacy: Definitions and Techniques' (2012) 20 International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems 793.

²⁶ Jianxi Luo, 'Data-Driven Innovation: What Is It?' (2023) 70 IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management 784.

technical development imposed by data-driven innovation,²⁷ which could contribute to a more effective regulatory and scholarly debate on tackling the spectrum of re-identification, while also making the best use of data without neglecting the dynamic nature of personal data.²⁸

The absence of such an approach often led to the creation of poorly anonymised personal data, leaving room for data misuses and abuses and, more generally, raised doubt or mistrust in anonymisation techniques. This does not neglect the argument, as pointed out by Purtova,²⁹ that any piece of data may contain an *information related to an identified or identifiable natural person*. Nevertheless, this argument makes it exceedingly difficult, if not impossible, to determine and ascertain the rules that ought to be applied to ensure adequate anonymisation, appearing to be as a too linear view of technology and technological development,³⁰ neglecting the fact that, in data driven innovation, data value may not depend only on the level of identifiability.³¹ More generally, the absence of a prescriptive approach leads to legal uncertainty and possibly liability risks, especially if operators who rely on the use of anonymised data are faced with the risk of being fined for processing (which eventually turns out to be) poorly anonymised data.

2.1. From zero risk to acceptable risk

In 2014, under the Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC,³² the WP29 provided guidance on the anonymisation techniques.³³ At that time, the WP29 defined anonymisation as the processing of personal data in such a way that re-identification is "irreversibly" prevented, given that identification should not only refer to the possibility of discovering an individual's name; identification also encompasses indirect identification through linkability, singling out or inference (p. 10).³⁴ Therefore, for personal data to be *truly*³⁵ anonymised, and thus for the EU data protection principles and rules not to apply, data subjects should be no longer identifiable after the processing of data that, hence, resulted anonymous.

According to the WP29, it was an "important factor" that the processing is "irreversible" (p. 5)³⁶ and that the "outcome of anonymisation" as a technique is (with regard to the state-of-the-art technology) "permanent as erasure" (p. 6),³⁷ hence suggesting an *absolute approach*. Still, it was already in this opinion that the WP29 acknowledged the *contextual* elements, which seems to be partially reflected into the wording of Recital 26 of the GDPR. Namely, when referring to "all means likely reasonably to be used for re-identification" through the controller or third parties. In this regard, *likely reasonably* necessitates *i. a.* to consider the availability and developments of the technological state-of-the-art due to the increasing computational power (p. 6, 7).³⁸ Thereby, the WP29 highlighted the limitations of existing

anonymisation techniques due to the *residual risk of re-identification* inherent to the controller and to third parties. To bring these risks forward, the WP29 seemed to prefer avoiding certain terminologies (i.e., *anonymity* or *anonymous data*), but instead referring to "anonymisation techniques" and stressing on the risk assessment procedure to tackle and minimise, at best, any kind of residual risk. Consequently, the difficulties linked to the successful implementation of the risk assessment procedure, as proposed by the GDPR, seem to be linked to the variety of outcomes in terms of personal data processing activities and their environment. In light of the above considerations, it is reasonable to argue that the European legislator faced many challenges to adopt a prescriptive approach to the re-identification test, rejecting the *a priori* determination of objective risk factors in the GDPR or other hard laws.

2.2. The European jurisprudence on anonymisation, anonymity, and re-identification

When personal data can be considered anonymous has also been debated in Court, especially focussed on the nature of processed personal data. While the WP29 Opinion³⁹ followed the so-called *absolute approach*, the approach taken by the Courts at the European level appears to provide a more practical solution to the difficulties in assessing the effectiveness of anonymisation techniques. Considering the contextual element in the re-identification test, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) is shaping the discussion on the anonymisation/pseudonymisation of personal data moving beyond WP29 Opinion.

In the *Breyer* case (C-582/14)⁴⁰ the CJEU had to determine whether a dynamic IP address constitutes personal data if a data controller has access to additional information enabling the re-identification of a data subject. The Court applied a wide interpretation of the concept of personal data and stressed that, for a third party, holding *legal means* to obtain relevant additional information enables the re-identification of a person.⁴¹ Consequently, to determine whether a natural person is re-identifiable, will depend on whether a party holds legal means to access additional information in the given context. This has sometimes been referred to as the *relative approach* to the concept of personal data.⁴²

Such a *relative approach* has been applied in other, most recent, court cases as well.

In April 2023, the General Court of the European Union referred in its judgment *SRB v EDPS* (Case T-557/20)⁴³ repeatedly referred to the legal means. More specifically, the Court held that it was necessary to assess whether a receiving party (acquiring processed personal data) has the legal means to also acquire additional information enabling the re-identification of a natural person. If so, the data would be considered personal data.⁴⁴

While this approach allows for a practical solution that enables data reuse, legal uncertainty could remain due to the discrepancy between the approach taken by the Court and the wording in legal texts. In fact, the decision refers to the data recipient, although the wording of the relevant Recital in the Regulation refers to the controller *or* the third party.

Similarly, in the case *Gesamtverband Autoteile-Handel eV. v Scania CV*

²⁷ *ibid.*

²⁸ Inge Graef, Raphaël Gellert and Martin Husovec, 'Towards a Holistic Regulatory Approach for the European Data Economy: Why the Illusive Notion of Non-Personal Data Is Counterproductive to Data Innovation' (2019) 44 *European Law Review* 605; *ibid.*

²⁹ Purtova, 'From Knowing by Name to Targeting' (n 6).

³⁰ Graef, Gellert and Husovec (n 28).

³¹ Raphaël Gellert, 'Personal Data's Ever-Expanding Scope in Smart Environments and Possible Path(s) for Regulating Emerging Digital Technologies' (2021) 11 *International Data Privacy Law* 196.

³² Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/1995/46/oj/eng>

³³ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (n 14).

³⁴ *ibid.*

³⁵ Italic added by the authors to confer emphasis.

³⁶ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (n 14).

³⁷ *ibid.*

³⁸ *ibid.*

³⁹ *ibid.*

⁴⁰ Case C-582/14, CJEU Judgment of the Court (Second Chamber) of 19 October 2016, Patrick Breyer v Bundesrepublik Deutschland.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, para. 49.

⁴² Finck and Pallas (n 6).

⁴³ Case T-557/20, CJEU Judgment of the General Court (Eight Chamber, Extended Composition) of 26 April 2023, Single Resolution Board v European Data Protection Supervisor.

⁴⁴ See, e.g., *ibid.*, para 97, 104-105.

AB (C-319/22)⁴⁵ the CJEU appears to be moving towards a more relative conceptualisation of personal data, determining that the question of whether data constitutes personal data must be assessed from the perspective of a third party. Whilst the Court stressed that a vehicle identification number does not constitute personal data *per se*,⁴⁶ here, again, it had to be determined if the operator at stake “may have means enabling him to use it to identify” by linking information (in this case, a vehicle identification number) to an identified or identifiable natural person.⁴⁷ Consequently, according to the Court, data can only be personal data if *associated* with or *related* to a natural person.⁴⁸

2.3. The concept of identifiability in the Digital Omnibus

The Digital Omnibus proposal represents an initiative to streamline the European data legislative *acquis*, following a simplified legislative procedure for market-integration objectives (*ex Art. 114 of the TFEU*).⁴⁹

The concept of personal data (and identifiability), framed in Art. 4 and in Recital 26 of the GDPR, fall within the scope of the Digital Omnibus. According to the proposed text, Art. 4 would be integrated by a further specification that integrates the orientation of the EU jurisprudence. The proposed text would clarify that “information relating to a natural person is not necessarily personal data for every other person or entity, merely because another entity can identify that natural person.”

The Digital Omnibus introduces a subjective approach, endorsing the idea that data is only personal to certain controllers, to certain third parties. In this regard, it further specifies that “Information shall not be personal for a given entity where that entity cannot identify the natural person to whom the information relates, taking into account the means reasonably likely to be used by that entity. Such information does not become personal for that entity merely because a potential subsequent recipient has means reasonably likely to be used to identify the natural person to whom the information relates”.

The lexical choices make it reasonable to consider that, even though data protection must usually be engineered according to the environment in question, security measures i.e. pseudonymisation of data (*ex Art. 32 of the GDPR*) play an essential role in determining the nature of the data and the applicable legal regime in context prone to data reuses. This becomes evident when analysing another key point of the Digital Omnibus: the proposed amendment to Recital 26 of the GDPR. Here, the European legislator challenges the original dichotomies relating to anonymisation/irreversibility and pseudonymisation/reversibility, which were introduced in the first internationally agreed set of privacy and data protection principles (the Council Recommendation on Guidelines Governing the Protection of Privacy and Transborder Flows of Personal Data), which was first endorsed in the Data Protection Directive and further recalled in the GDPR. In fact, the mere existence of additional information that could enable identification of the data subject does not mean that pseudonymised data must always be regarded as personal data for the purposes of Regulation (EU) 2016/679. Hence, if the risk of identification is insignificant, either because identification of the data subject is prohibited by law or impossible in practice, the data cannot be considered personal.

This line of reasoning and interpretation is also confirmed by other proposed modifications of the data legislative *acquis* presented in the Digital Omnibus, among which Art. 35 and Art. 41(a) of the GDPR.

⁴⁵ Case C-319/22, CJEU Judgment of the Court (Third Chamber) of 9 November 2023, *Gesamtverband Autoteile-Handel eV. v Scania CV AB*.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*, para 46.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*, para. 48.

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*, para 46.

⁴⁹ Although a non-regression clause does not appear in the Digital Omnibus text, according to the European legal *acquis* the simplification cannot reduce existing levels of protection of personal data and privacy.

While the former aims at centralising and streamlining a new procedure that transfers the obligation for national supervisory authorities to compile lists of processing operations that do (or do not) require a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) to the EDPB. The EDPB then submits these lists to the Commission for adoption. The latter must be interpreted in conjunction with the modification envisaged for Art. 4 of the GDPR, providing that the Commission defines, through an implementing act, what no longer constitutes ‘personal data’, deeming pseudonymisation techniques to be sufficient to render data anonymous.

In addition to these proposed amendments to the GDPR, the Digital Omnibus Act suggests repealing the Data Governance Act (DGA) and incorporating the provisions concerning DISPs into the Data Act.⁵⁰ Despite this transposition, the European data governance model originally set out in the 2020 European Strategy for Data and put forward with the DGA remains in place, with anonymisation serving as the access gate to the further reuse of data.

3. Anonymisation in the light of the Data Governance Act

Over time, the academic debate on anonymisation has involved several scientific communities. As anticipated, within the legal community the debate seemed to be somewhat polarised already for several decades: some scholars argue that anonymisation is unattainable due to the technological advancements in re-identification techniques and de-anonymisation attacks while others sustain that a trade-off between data utility and data protection could be reached. Within the latter, particularly Ohm⁵¹ stressed “the failure of anonymisation” due to the increase of sophisticated de-anonymisation techniques enabling reverse engineering of anonymisation processing. On the other hand, Cavoukian⁵² stressed on considering anonymisation a reliable data processing operation, despite the growing reversibility risk.

In the last years, this debate has been enriched by different perspectives that built on this polarisation rooted in Ohm and Cavoukian research lines. Recently, for instance, Purtova⁵³ highlights how the constraints of anonymisation⁵⁴ represent the main foundation of the in-force legislation on personal and non-personal data, where identifiability is the “de-facto threshold condition” for determining the status of data as personal. In fact, Purtova⁵⁵ considers that these constraints challenge the compliance regime imposed by the GDPR and, by the time, leading to lastly abandon the difference between personal and non-personal data, given that any data and any data processing operation may require protection. In this regard, Graef⁵⁶ and Gellert⁵⁷ clarify that the dynamic nature of personal data increases its ever-expanding scope and that a holistic regulatory approach should rather tackle the concept of non-personal data as mutually exclusive with the one of personal data. They consider the former counterproductive for the data-driven innovation,⁵⁸ given that it creates a risk of strategic over-compliance with data protection law. According to their line of reasoning, in such development scenario data value does not depend entirely on the level of identifiability in data, imposing not to neglect that data innovation has many dimensions that cannot be restricted exclusively on data

⁵⁰ Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/2394 and Directive (EU) 2020/1828 (Data Act), available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854/oj/eng>

⁵¹ Ohm (n 24).

⁵² Cavoukian and El Emam (n 25).

⁵³ Purtova, ‘From Knowing by Name to Targeting’ (n 6).

⁵⁴ Ohm (n 24).

⁵⁵ Purtova, ‘The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law’ (n 6).

⁵⁶ Graef, Gellert and Husovec (n 28).

⁵⁷ Gellert, ‘Personal Data’s Ever-Expanding Scope in Smart Environments and Possible Path(s) for Regulating Emerging Digital Technologies’ (n 31).

⁵⁸ Luo (n 26).

protection ground.⁵⁹

Hence, given that the entire environment is becoming data-driven, associated with Web 3.0 (also known as the Semantic Web or the Internet of Things, aka IoT),⁶⁰ the purpose of the processing becomes the essential element when assessing the identifiability of anonymised data, which also directly enables the assessment and minimisation of any form of automated decision-making.⁶¹ This would make trust a prerequisite for any kind of data exchange, shifting the focus from processing itself to modelling threats in these new data-driven scenarios.⁶² This approach could be strengthened by quantifying the implementation of technical and organisational measures⁶³ to ensure data anonymity in each environment, facilitating the allocation of roles and responsibilities among participating stakeholders.

Along this line of reasoning, Rupp⁶⁴ considers that the specific *purpose* of processing plays an essential role in assessing the risk to a fundamental right of an individual to determine whether data falls into the scope of application of the GDPR. This consideration appears to be sustainable especially if considering, for instance, the processing undertaken by a public sector entity pursuing public interests, and the processing undertaken by a private sector entity pursuing business aims. For instance, this is the case of the processing for statistical purposes pursued by public entities, and namely National Statistical Institutes (NSI), whose legal nature and public scope make them trustful - thus *de-facto* more accountable and reliable in terms of processing, due to the fact that these entities are subject to transparency measures in the exertion of their public functions.⁶⁵

Already in 2018 Elliot⁶⁶ suggests a contextual approach to anonymisation called “functional anonymisation” which focuses on the data environment, where the contextual element refers mainly to the relationship between data and the environment within which the data exists. This line of reasoning seems to mirror the approach of the CJEU and, perhaps, also the most recent technical literature on the topic.⁶⁷ Elliot⁶⁸ highlights that, from a technical perspective, no perfect solution exists for anonymisation and that the application of modern techniques and auditing procedures to safeguard against threats represent the best option to ensure the secure use and exchange of data today.

In line with all the above considerations, it cannot be left unspoken the main paradigm under which anonymisation techniques are being developed: security tests on anonymised data imply the breach of data protection techniques. In this regard, scholars from the statistical community and the computer science community keep on proposing new

anonymisation techniques. This renders reasonable to argue that strengthening legal accountability measures could be a good option for backing up the uncertainty pertaining to anonymisation as *imperfect science*.⁶⁹ Changes and challenges brought by the *onlife* paradigm,⁷⁰ the *datafication* process,⁷¹ and the *data-driven innovation*⁷² appear to require a new contextualisation and conceptualisation of data anonymisation, given the ubiquitous nature of data and its scalable collection and processing. Thus, anonymisation must evolve physiologically into a socio-technical component of data governance.⁷³ In fact, the *onlife* paradigm,⁷⁴ the *datafication* process,⁷⁵ and *data-driven innovation*⁷⁶ impose anonymisation as a mean of facilitating data exchange. For this exchange to be trustworthy, roles, potential liabilities and ethical responsibilities of the parties⁷⁷ involved in the collection, processing and reuse of data must be clearly defined, given that risk assessment alone is no longer suitable in emerging scenarios.

This advocated evolution of anonymisation requires a cross-functional perspective that broadens the view beyond organisational legal compliance boundaries and levels⁷⁸ in data processing and, more broadly, data management, as imposed on the entity collecting the data in the first place. In this regard, the DGA appears to provide a suitable basis for redefining anonymisation.

3.1. The Data gGovernance Act and its frame on re-identification within intermediation

The DGA represents one of the main pillars of the EU’s Strategy for Data,⁷⁹ applicable since September 2023, and seeking to support the establishment of common European Data Spaces across different domains of European strategic interest. The DGA is a horizontal legislative measure, to be complemented by sectoral legislation that applies to each strategic sector, where roles and responsibilities of data holders are

⁵⁹ Purtova, ‘The Law of Everything. Broad Concept of Personal Data and Future of EU Data Protection Law’ (n 6).

⁶⁰ Luciano Floridi (ed), *The Onlife Manifesto* (Springer International Publishing 2015).

⁶¹ Viktor Mayer-Schoenberger and Kenneth Cukier, *Big Data. A Revolution That Will Transform How We Live, Work, and Think*. (John Murray Publishers 2013).

⁶² Luo (n 26).

⁶³ Luciano Floridi, ‘Soft Ethics and the Governance of the Digital’ (2018) 31 *Philosophy & Technology* 1; Gregory Vial, ‘Understanding Digital Transformation: A Review and a Research Agenda’ (2019) 28 *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems* 118; Rene Abraham, Johannes Schneider and Jan Vom Brocke, ‘Data Governance: A Conceptual Framework, Structured Review, and Research Agenda’ (2019) 49 *International Journal of Information Management* 424; Marina Micheli and others, ‘Emerging Models of Data Governance in the Age of Datafication’ (2020) 7 *Big Data & Society*; Salome Viljoen, ‘A Relational Theory of Data Governance Feature’ (2021) 131 *Yale Law Journal* 573; Gregory Vial, ‘Data Governance and Digital Innovation: A Translational Account of Practitioner Issues for IS Research’ (2023) 33 *Inf. Organ.* 100450.

⁶⁴ Floridi (n 70).

⁶⁵ Mayer-Schoenberger and Cukier (n 71).

⁶⁶ Luo (n 26).

⁶⁷ Roland L Trope and E Michael Power, ‘Lessons in Data Governance: A Survey of Legal Developments in Data Management, Privacy and Security’ (2005) 61 *The Business Lawyer* 471.

⁶⁸ Balázs Bodó and others, ‘Personal Data Ordering in Context: The Interaction of Meso-Level Data Governance Regimes with Macro Frameworks’ (2021) 10 *Internet Policy Review*.

⁶⁹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. A European Strategy for Data. Brussels, 19.11.2025 COM(2025) 837 final, 2025/0360(COD). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0837>

⁵⁹ Graef, Gellert and Husovec (n 28); Gellert, ‘Personal Data’s Ever-Expanding Scope in Smart Environments and Possible Path(s) for Regulating Emerging Digital Technologies’ (n 31).

⁶⁰ Luo (n 26).

⁶¹ Graef, Gellert and Husovec (n 28); Gellert, ‘Personal Data’s Ever-Expanding Scope in Smart Environments and Possible Path(s) for Regulating Emerging Digital Technologies’ (n 31).

⁶² Emanuela Podda, ‘Data Governance and Neutral Data Intermediation: Legal Properties and Potential Semantic Constraints’ in Meiko Jensen, Cédric Lauradoux and Kai Rannenberg (eds), *Privacy Technologies and Policy*, vol 14831 (Springer Nature Switzerland 2024).

⁶³ Nils Holzenberger and Winston Maxwell, ‘A Quantitative Approach to the GDPR’s Anonymisation and “Appropriate Technical and Organisational Measures” Tests’ (2025) 59 *Computer Law & Security Review* 106173.

⁶⁴ Valentin Rupp and Max Von Grafenstein, ‘Clarifying “Personal Data” and the Role of Anonymisation in Data Protection Law Including and Excluding Data from the Scope of the GDPR (More Clearly) through Refining the Concept of Data Protection’ (2024) 52 *Computer Law & Security Review* 105932.

⁶⁵ Emanuela Podda, ‘Shedding Light on the Legal Approach to Aggregate Data under the GDPR & the FFDR.’, *UNECE, Conference of European Statisticians, Expert Meeting on Statistical Data Confidentiality* (2021).

⁶⁶ Mark Elliot and others, ‘Functional Anonymisation: Personal Data and the Data Environment’ (2018) 34 *Computer Law and Security Review* 204.

⁶⁷ Gadotti and others (n 3).

⁶⁸ Elliot and others (n 66).

more ingrained due to sector peculiarities. The Impact Assessment accompanying the initial DGA proposal⁸⁰ showed that the lack of trust in exchanging data⁸¹ increased transaction costs, challenging the development of interoperability solutions for cleaning, transforming, and sharing data. In line with these premises, the DGA seeks to increase trust in data exchange, facilitating the flow of specific categories of data held by public sector bodies, thus unleashing its value and harnessing its potential due to legitimate further reuses.

3.1.1. Re-identification risks and the role of intermediaries

The DGA sets up organizational means to incentivize the voluntary sharing of data between different actors whose interactions should be based on mutual trust. It does not create any obligation on public sector bodies to grant the re-use of data, nor does it release public sector bodies from their confidentiality duties under Union or national law⁸². Whilst relying on voluntary mechanisms of participation, the DGA strengthens trustworthiness in data access and data sharing between parties involved in data transactions by:

- a) defining conditions for the reuse of specific categories of data held by public sector bodies;
- b) introducing the role of Data Intermediation Service Providers (DISPs)⁸³ based on a notification and supervisory framework;
- c) introducing the role of Data Altruism Organizations (DAOs) that collect, and process data made available for altruistic purposes, based on a voluntary registration mechanism.

The DGA applies to public entities holding specific categories of data⁸⁴ whose nature should be protected and whose processing may justify the charge of fees.

Within these particular categories of data held by public sector

⁸⁰ Commission Staff Working Document, Executive Summary of the Impact Assessment Report Accompanying the document Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on European Data Governance (Data Governance Act). Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020SC0296>

⁸¹ Data sharing is broadly conceived, including also accessing data.

⁸² See extensively, *ibid.*, Article 5 of the Data Governance Act.

⁸³ Though the responsibilities and organization specificities in terms of the data intermediaries may still not be entirely comprehensible, the general idea is that these institutions act as trustworthy third parties facilitating data access and sharing between data providers (e.g., data subjects, or legal persons as data holders) and data users. Specifically, Article 5 DGA implements three main requirements for data re-use: granting access and re-use of data only after ensuring data anonymisation (for personal data), data modification or aggregation or processing by a Disclosure Control method (for commercially confidential information, trade secrets or intellectual property rights) (1); granting access and re-use of data remotely within a secure processing environment (provided by the controller or by the public sector body) (2); granting access and re-use of data within the physical premises of the public sector body where a secure processing environment is located (high security standards and access control should be ensured) (3). Thereby, the DGA, which envisages an organizational framework for granting data re-use, draws clear boundaries in data access and sharing with the aim of unleashing the potential of data by imposing specific conditions on organizations wishing to share and grant access to their data.

⁸⁴ Article 3 of the DGA clarifies that data re-use is not foreseen for a) data held by public undertakings, b) data held by public service broadcasters and their subsidiaries, and by other bodies and their subsidiaries for the fulfilment of a public service broadcasting remit, c) data held by cultural establishment and educational establishment, d) data held by public sector bodies which are protected for reasons of public security, defence, or national security, e) data the supply of which is an activity falling outside the scope of the public task of the public sector bodies concerned as defined by law or by other binding rules in the Member State concerned, or, in the absence of such rules, as defined in accordance with common administrative practice in that Member State, provided that the scope of the public tasks is transparent and subject to review.

entities that invoke various legal bases for protection, the DGA enumerates:

- a) personal data protected under the GDPR;
- b) data protected by commercial and statistical confidentiality;
- c) data protected by intellectual property rights of third parties.

To grant availability and re-use of such data, *ex Art. 5*, public sector bodies are requested to preserve the nature of protected data. Specifically for personal data protected under the GDPR, that is the main focus of this article, public sector bodies are required to anonymise data, or to grant access and re-use of data within a *secure processing environment* provided or controlled by the public sector body.⁸⁵ Recital 7 provides guidance in the interpretation of Art. 5, highlighting that the analysis on databases containing personal data may be enabled by relying on “anonymisation techniques, differential privacy, generalisation, suppression and randomisation, synthetic data, or other state-of-of-the-art privacy-preserving methods that can contribute to a more privacy-friendly processing of data”. The same Recital clarifies that “such techniques, combined with comprehensive data protection impact assessments and other safeguards, can increase safety in the use and re-use of personal data”, although the state-of-the-art of anonymisation techniques and privacy-friendly-processing of data do not seem to be integrated into the regulatory setting.

The DGA draws a data governance model that creates an additional and overarching regulatory layer on other regulatory frameworks that protect specific categories of data, included personal data, for which anonymisation represents an access gate to multiple further reuses of data. In this regard, Art. 5 in conjunction with Recital 15 of the DGA, clarifies that public entities are required to anonymise data before transmission, therefore they are bound by this legal obligation. A literal interpretation of this provision suggests that public entities must verify whether anonymisation is required for the reuse of data. This means that public entities must first determine what kind of reuse/processing the data user intends to undertake and assess the level of risk that this would entail. According to the letter of the law, data can only be reused at a raw level if anonymisation is not required for the reuse and the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) shows that the risk of re-identification is minimal, provided that reuse takes place within a secure processing environment set up on-premises or remotely (see Fig. 1).

According to the letter of the law, assessing the risk of re-identification requires striking a fair balance between the needs of data holders and data reusers. Such a provision must avoid creating unequal and imbalanced bargaining power among the parties, as this could undermine the fairness of contractual security, privacy and data protection when exchanging data. The DGA anticipates a scenario in which a neutral third party could conduct such an analysis, mediating data transactions between data holders and users. This third party would provide data intermediation services (Articles 10 to 14) aiming at mitigating various aspects of inter-organisational data exchanges.

3.1.2. Data intermediaries from a multi-disciplinary point of view

In legal scholar literature,⁸⁶ Carovano defines a data intermediary as “any entity that provides a data intermediation service, a middleman that interposes data holders and data users to facilitate the exchange of data [...]”. More generally, Giannopoulou⁸⁷ clarifies that the concept of data intermediary is used in several contexts, referring to “organizations

⁸⁵ Such access and re-use may be granted remotely or within the physical premises in which the secure processing environment is located.

⁸⁶ Gabriele Carovano and Michèle Finck, ‘Regulating Data Intermediaries: The Impact of the Data Governance Act on the EU’s Data Economy’ (2023) 50 *Computer Law & Security Review* 105830.

⁸⁷ Alexandra Giannopoulou and others, ‘Intermediating Data Rights Exercises: The Role of Legal Mandates’ (2022) 12 *International Data Privacy Law* 316.

Fig. 1. Diagram on anonymisation and re-identification risk ex DGA.

that capitalize on pooling data [...], assisting in the (collective) exercise of data rights, whether it be the right to object, erasure, portability, or indeed access personal data". Following this line of reasoning, Giannopoulou highlights how contract law and fiduciary duties may be explored for shaping appropriate environments where data intermediaries regulate data rights. Specifically in this respect, the intermediary role may initiate a paradigm shift in anonymisation as a socio-technical component in emerging scenarios of data-driven innovation, moving from data privacy to data control and data re-use. For Micheli,⁸⁸ data control and data re-use are concepts embedded in data governance that are conceived as "a social-science informed definition, as the set of rules, policies, legal mechanisms, stakeholder relationships, decision-making structures and processes established to collect, share and use data". This definition, introduced within the social sciences domain, seems to intersect with the conceptualisation of data management in computer science where data governance refers to the authority and control over the management of data as a *cross-functional effort*.⁸⁹ Data governance determines how data can be made available to third parties for re-uses outside of the organisational boundaries of the entity that collects data in the first place. Data governance aims at creating value from data, permitting the distribution of its value among stakeholders, in an accountable and responsible manner, relying on means ranging from consent forms to policies, technical standards and contractual agreements. In this regard, the DGA and the role it designed for DISPs may contribute to initiating a paradigm shift in anonymisation by

conferring more certainty and accountability.

3.2. Data intermediaries under the DGA

The DGA imposes that public entities whose data are protected under the GDPR anonymise their data before transmission. As previously discussed, this obligation can be derived from Art. 5(3)(a) and Recital 15 of the DGA, as well as the principles and rules imposed by the GDPR for personal data. Since the GDPR lacks prescriptive standards for data anonymisation, it is reasonable to consider that legal vacuums may propagate in the scenarios envisaged by the DGA, where public entities hold data and are obliged to anonymise it for re-uses. Considering that this activity is strictly tied to the accountability principle ex Art. 5 of the GDPR, the legal uncertainty linked to data anonymisation may undermine the level of trust placed in the entities required to undertake anonymisation processing.

3.2.1. The role of a third-party intermediary

The DGA foresees the case where the obligation to anonymise data can be fulfilled by a third party, namely the DISP as a *neutral* party responsible for data intermediation services. Article 2(11) of the DGA defines data intermediation service as "a service that aims to establish commercial relationships for data sharing between an undetermined number of data subjects and data holders on the one hand, and data users on the other, through technical, legal or other means [...]".

DISPs facilitate bilateral or multilateral exchanges of data, or the creation of platforms or databases enabling the exchange or joint use of data, as well as the establishment of other specific infrastructures for the interconnection of data holders and data users, as envisioned by Article 10 of the DGA. Article 12(e) of the DGA clarifies that such intermediation services may include specific tools or services for facilitating data

⁸⁸ Micheli and others (n 73); Micheli and others (n 13).

⁸⁹ Abraham, Schneider and Vom Brocke (n 73); Vial (n 73); Rene Abraham, Johannes Schneider and Jan Vom Brocke, 'A Taxonomy of Data Governance Decision Domains in Data Marketplaces' (2023) 33 *Electronic Markets* 22.

exchange, such as data anonymisation, if explicitly requested or approved by the data holder, and under several specific conditions *ex Art. 12. Carovano*⁹⁰ highlights that, in the context foreseen by the DGA, the intermediation service is provided by a “middleman” interposed between data holders and data users that “facilitates the exchange of data between parties in a neutral fashion way”. By doing so, the intermediary fulfils the role of a mediator between those who hold data and those who wish to leverage data, permitting data re-purposing, re-contextualization, and re-uses.

The DGA specifies that the intermediation services may be realised between data subjects that seek to make their personal data available, or data holders or natural persons that seek to make non-personal data available, as well as refer to the services typically provided by data cooperatives. This implies that the DGA does not favour a specific business model, thereby providing a margin of appreciation for stakeholders aiming at setting up data intermediation services. Article 12 clarifies that the aim of such activities should be establishing a *commercial relationship* for the purpose of data sharing, through technical, legal, or other means. Framed as *commercial*, this activity differs from the one of Data Altruism Organizations (or other not-for-profit entities).⁹¹

3.2.2. Intermediation and responsibility

The DGA highlights that the data intermediary holds responsibilities for data sharing and data access activities. Article 12(e) DGA illustrates various and additional services that an intermediary can provide, such as, for instance, supporting stakeholders for pseudonymisation and anonymisation of data, or rendering available a secure processing environment as a specific infrastructure provided or controlled by the public sector body holding data (Recital 7).⁹² Therefore public entities wishing to make their data available for re-uses could rely on the intermediation services provided by the DISPs.

In this regard, ENISA clarifies that data holders may assign different roles and responsibilities to intermediaries, some of which may be more active than others.⁹³ This prompts the question of what level of responsibility data intermediaries derive from anonymising data, for processing data *stricto sensu*. Article 7(3) DGA requires that competent bodies shall make “adequate legal, financial, technical and human resources to carry out the tasks assigned to them”. In principle, data intermediaries are required to make the necessary arrangements to protect personal data from disclosure, unlawful or unauthorized access or similar challenges, even if an intermediary acts as a third “intermediate/connecting” party that shares data from other stakeholders.⁹⁴ At the same time, Recital 33 DGA considers the neutrality of data intermediation services providers a “key element” with regard to the data exchanged between data holders or data subjects and data users, as neutrality seeks to increase trust and data control. Notably, caution seems to be needed when implementing the neutrality requirement from

a technical standpoint,⁹⁵ since DISPs may rely on cloud services for providing the intermediation services.⁹⁶ This scenario requires further investigation on the allocation of roles and responsibilities, as well as on threat modelling and detection, as it brings new security and privacy risks and challenges.⁹⁷

The letter of the law requires that, to enforce neutrality, data intermediation services providers should not use the data exchanged for any other purpose, and that structural separation between data intermediation services is enforced in order to avoid a potential conflict of interest.⁹⁸ More importantly, data intermediation services bear fiduciary duties to ensure that they act in the best interest of the data subjects. Considering these features, one might argue that data intermediation services may have to enforce an *absolute approach* with regard to data anonymisation, also to avoid potential liability (e.g., laid down in contracts).⁹⁹ Yet, the role and responsibilities of data intermediaries are somewhat unexplored since data intermediaries’ governance practices are still evolving.¹⁰⁰

4. Anonymisation under a new guise

Given the possibility for DISPs to anonymise data before sharing data or to control and manage access to a secure processing environment where data is protected¹⁰¹ (see Fig. 1), several aspects concerning data governance have yet to be investigated. For instance, once the data holder grants access to raw-level data to DISPs, questions arise as to what the agreement between data users and DISPs should entail.

Whilst this article does not aim to constitute a compliance tool, the following section will reflect and elaborate upon different aspects pertinent to facilitating data anonymisation in legal practice, that may be recalled in the contractual agreement between the parties with the primary scope of data governance *ex DGA*.

4.1. Legal aspects pertinent to anonymisation under the GDPR and the DGA

To identify legal aspects that are pertinent to facilitate data anonymisation, the responsibilities of both, data users and DISPs, need to be clearly determined disentangling legal knots arising from the contextual application of the DGA and the GDPR. Specific consideration must be given to the European jurisprudence illustrated above, and the concrete risks that must be identified by data holders (*ex DGA*) in their role as data controllers (*ex GDPR*). Subsequently, the DISPs will anonymise data before sharing it (entailing a secure transferring) or control the

⁹⁰ Carovano and Finck (n 86).

⁹¹ These services are also introduced and regulated by the DGA, and they aim at supporting the collection of data for objectives of general interest. This type of service may carry additional responsibilities which, in the light of the scope of this article, will not be further investigated.

⁹² Art. 2 Section 20 defines as secure processing environment “the physical or virtual environment and organisational means to ensure compliance with Union law, such as Regulation (EU) 2016/679, in particular with regard to data subjects’ rights, intellectual property rights, and commercial and statistical confidentiality, integrity and accessibility, as well as with applicable national law, and to allow the entity providing the secure processing environment to determine and supervise all data processing actions, including the display, storage, download and export of data and the calculation of derivative data through computational algorithms; [...]”.

⁹³ ENISA European Agency for Cybersecurity, ‘Engineering Personal Data Protection in EU Data Spaces’ (2024) Report/Study.

⁹⁴ For instance, recital 20 DGA, Article 5(5) DGA.

⁹⁵ Podda, ‘Data Governance and Neutral Data Intermediation’ (n 62).

⁹⁶ This scenario should also be considered as directly concerning the provision of data intermediation service covered by the DGA. Contrarily, as specified by the same Recital, it should be distinguished by “[t]he provision of cloud storage, analytics, data sharing software, web browsers, browser plug-ins or email services should not be considered to be data intermediation services within the meaning of this Regulation, provided that such services only provide technical tools for data subjects or data holders to share data with others, but the provision of such tools neither aims to establish a commercial relationship between data holders and data users nor allows the data intermediation services provider to acquire information on the establishment of commercial relationships for the purposes of data sharing [...]”.

⁹⁷ Sabrina De Capitani di Vimercati, Sara Foresti and Pierangela Samarati, ‘Protecting Data and Queries in Cloud-Based Scenarios’ (2023) 4 SN Computer Science 440.

⁹⁸ Recital 33 DGA.

⁹⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁰ Micheli and others (n 13).

¹⁰¹ Recital 7 of the DGA envisages that the secure processing environment is provided or controlled by the public sector body. If *provided*, the control may be exerted by the DISP, while if *controlled* the provision may be granted by the DISP.

access to data (managing a secure processing environment).

In the case of secure transferring, the question of whether anonymised data is anonymous is twofold.

First, considering Recital 26 of the GDPR with the EU jurisprudence endorsed by the Digital Omnibus, the question is whether anonymity can be upheld will depend on the means likely to be reasonably used, for which the technical advancements also must be considered. Furthermore, as discussed earlier, it must be assessed whether the data recipient (reuser ex DGA) has the legal means to obtain additional information to identify a person (data subject). Therefore, to determine whether data is anonymous, data controllers must, on one hand, assess the technological advancement and, on the other hand, assess if the data reuser has the legal means to (potentially) obtain additional information enabling re-identification. The latter may even require contractual arrangements to ensure that data users abstain from requesting such information unless the law explicitly provides for it. Only if both aspects can be positively answered, it is reasonable to sustain that the anonymisation of personal data has been achieved, considering data as anonymous. Otherwise, where the objective of the processing purpose cannot be met with personal data (Recital 15 of the DGA), or where personal data cannot be anonymised, the data user will be obliged to carry out a DPIA. Article 35 of the GDPR requires to proceed with a DPIA when the processing is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals (data subjects). Arguably, keeping data anonymous is a challenge with large-scale data sharing,¹⁰² reason that could have justified the modification of Art. 35 with the Digital Omnibus proposal.

To minimise the risks, specific contract clauses may be added to the agreements¹⁰³ regulating data sharing for exchanging data between data holders and DISPs. In this regard, the spirit of the DGA and letter of the law may orientate and assist the parties in defining such contractual clauses as illustrated in Table 1.

The inclusion of specific clauses in the agreement could vary depending on a party's interests, as well as on the execution of the contract. Data anonymity enables data exchange, but it does not mean that data can be further disclosed just because it is considered anonymous. In fact, the required level of anonymisation will depend on the concerned level of data confidentiality, as well as on the environment in which it will be processed, for which the re-identification risk could vary. Though parties may address these legal elements differently on a case-by-case basis, one could, in principle, distinguish between a *preparatory phase* and a *monitoring phase*.

4.1.1. Preparatory phase

In the light of the general clauses that can be directly derived from the DGA (see Table 1), DISPs will have to take into account the data reusers' circumstances, the degree of confidentiality in data, the technical means to be applied, and the purpose for which they seek to process the data in order to assess the adequacy of anonymisation. This is reflected in Recitals 15 and 24 DGA, considering that certain personal data held by public sector bodies may be highly confidential (e.g. for transfer to third countries) and could lead to several risks.

If legal compliance can be achieved, and data may be finally shared, will depend on the required and agreed level of anonymisation. Thus, it is reasonable to consider that the data reusers will need to illustrate *reasons* and *means* to use anonymised data. Vice-versa, the DISP should be bound to inform the data reuser about the risk of de-anonymisation.

¹⁰² René Raab and others, 'Federated Electronic Health Records for the European Health Data Space' (2023) 5 The Lancet Digital Health e840.

¹⁰³ Within the framework of the DGA, the European Commission has already established the EU Register of Data Intermediation Services, available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-intermediary-services> Within this list, data intermediation services recall different kinds of agreements, some of which framed as *Data Intermediation Service Agreement*, some others as *Data Contract Service* (as in the case of Gaia X).

Table 1

General clauses that may be added to the agreement regulating data sharing for transacting data between data holders and DISPs.

General clauses	
General Scope of the Regulation	Explain the objective for sharing data and why the data is necessary to achieve the objective. State the parties, their roles (e.g., controller or processor) and responsibilities.
Recital 8 and 15 DGA, Article 5(5) DGA	Re-identification of individuals from anonymised datasets should be prohibited. This applies also to pseudonymous data (e.g., if the transfer of anonymous data did not meet the re-user's needs). If a data subject is re-identified, then the public sector bodies must be informed about the data breach (in addition to the notification requirement under the GDPR).
Recital 9 DGA	Promote the creation and procurement of data in formats and structures that facilitate anonymisation.
Recital 15 DGA	Whilst the re-use of data should be facilitated based on consent of the data subject or permission of the data holder, no contact information should be given to enable re-users to contact data subjects or data holders.
Recital 36 and 37 DGA	Impose penalties for fraudulent or abusive practices (e.g., measures such as the exclusion of data users breaching the terms of service or infringing existing law). Also, transpose measures to ensure compliance with competition law.
Recital 38 DGA	Transpose relevant clauses to ensure efficient facilitation of the DISP's notification procedure, considering the principle of non-discrimination.

Appointing someone with adequate seniority and technical and legal knowledge to administer the anonymisation process can support the implementation of anonymisation techniques and provide legal protection in the fulfilment of this obligation.

Differently (Table 2), in case the DISP provides and control a secure processing environment (as explicitly recalled in Art. 5 and Recital 7 of the DGA).¹⁰⁴ In this case data will be kept in DISP premises and the reusers will have access to raw level data: each specific computation can be controlled by the DISP, ensuring full auditability.

4.1.2. Monitoring Phase

The responsibilities of the DISP, for the monitoring phase, should be neither limited to the pre-transmission phase, nor to the transmission as such. After sharing anonymised data, the DISP should maintain the responsibility to monitor the data re-users' activities, requiring that, during this phase, the DISP supervises data users to ensure the legitimate enforcement of the contract. The degree of monitoring responsibilities would depend on the level of anonymisation defined during the preparatory phase. When data sharing is not envisaged and data remains in DISP premises, for instance, Recital 15 of the DGA suggests that entities should supervise data analyses in secure processing environments to protect the rights and interests of third parties.

It seems reasonable to argue that the monitoring phase should permit reiteration of the evaluation of data transactions and ensure that the parties re-assess the context within which the data transactions take place. After all, Recital 15 of the DGA stresses that non-personal data should only be transmitted if "there is no reason to believe that the combination of non-personal data sets would lead to the identification of data subjects".

Given the nature of the activities carried out by the DISP, the DISP responsibility could vary depending on whether data is transferred or processed in DISP premises.

In case of data sharing (*sensu stricto*), the nature of the obligation of

¹⁰⁴ The DGA envisages the case in which the public entity provides the secure processing environment (case that falls under the scope of investigation), as well as the case in which the public entity controls (case that falls out of the scope of investigation).

Table 2
Preparatory phase.

Data is not kept in DISP premises	Data is kept in DISP premises (SPE)
Before transmission, personal data should be anonymised, and commercially confidential data should be modified in a way that no confidential information is disclosed (Recital 15 DGA). Identification of applicable legal basis by the data provider for sharing personal data with the intermediary and by the intermediary for the data anonymisation	Identification of applicable legal basis by data provider for sharing personal data with the intermediary and by the intermediary for the data anonymisation
If disclosure is planned towards multiple parties, assess the risks for re-identification based on the planned (and previous) disclosures	Identify the risks taking into account the type of access that is being granted (e.g., access to raw data, federated learning, etc) and to what type of data access is being granted (e.g., personal data, anonymous data). If anonymised data does not respond to the needs of the re-user, on-premise or remote re-use via a secure processing environment could be allowed provided the relevant requirements (e.g., DPIA, consultation with DPA as per Article 35 and 36 GDPR) are fulfilled (Recital 15 DGA)
Identify the adequate anonymisation technique and describe the technique chosen	
If applicable (depending also on the legal basis building the foundation for the anonymisation), inform the individual about the anonymisation of their personal data	

the third intermediary could be considered as an *obligation of means*, given that the DISP does not retain control over the data once the data leaves the DISP premises. In this case, the intermediary can still provide penalties for illegitimate de-anonymization going beyond eligible contracted operations, if any form of control for further processing activities could be included in the contractual arrangement. Contrarily, in case the DISP controls the secure processing environment without any sharing the data, the nature of the obligation of the third intermediary could be considered as an *obligation of result*, given that data does not leave DISP premises and the DISP retains control over data. In this case, the monitoring ensures that no further operations are performed on the data in addition to the eligible contracted operations.

Certainly, in both cases, the allocation of responsibilities impacts on the burden of proof.

4.2. Contractual arrangements ex DGA

Although the DGA does not recall specific contractual arrangements, such arrangements are often defined as Data Sharing Agreements (DSA) in scientific literature.¹⁰⁵ They aim at regulating initiatives to pool or link together data and render it available for further re-uses. These arrangements can be set up in bilateral (between data providers and data users) or multilateral (between data providers and data users)

¹⁰⁵ Marina Egea and others, 'Definition of Data Sharing Agreements' in Massimo Felici and Carmen Fernández-Gago (eds), *Accountability and Security in the Cloud: First Summer School, Cloud Accountability Project, A4Cloud, Malaga, Spain, June 2-6, 2014, Revised Selected Papers and Lectures* (Springer International Publishing 2015); Claudio Caimi and others, 'Legal and Technical Perspectives in Data Sharing Agreements Definition' in Bettina Berendt and others (eds), *Privacy Technologies and Policy* (Springer International Publishing 2016); Jose Fran Ruiz and others, 'A Lifecycle for Data Sharing Agreements: How It Works Out' in Stefan Schiffner and others (eds), *Privacy Technologies and Policy* (Springer International Publishing 2016).

agreements. They could integrate different characteristics when regulating terms and conditions of data sharing and accessing data, depending on the business model they reflect.¹⁰⁶

In legal practice, several examples can be recalled. For instance, if data is kept on premises, an agreement is often referred to as a Data Access Agreement (DAA).¹⁰⁷ If data is not kept on premises and transmitted to the re-user, the reference is made to a Data Use Agreement (DUA),¹⁰⁸ Data Sharing Agreement (DSA),¹⁰⁹ or Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)¹¹⁰ depending on the specific ecosystem of application, the corporate model and contractual mechanisms. Such contractual arrangements seem not to be harmonised in legal practice, and public and private entities are currently exploring the issue.¹¹¹

In addition to the lack of clarity created through the diversity in legal and contractual arrangements and archetypes (based on specific business models and data governance models),¹¹² specific taxonomies or typologies have yet to be investigated as they are currently in flux. To address this drawback, for instance, frameworks for data sharing agreements, such as the one created by GovLab,¹¹³ can provide a fundament to establish legal clauses for data sharing agreements. The so-called "Contractual Wheel of Data Collaboration" considers relevant legal aspects such as access criteria, rights and responsibilities, governance and audit, or risk mitigation strategies.¹¹⁴ Within this setting, incorporating specific clauses on data anonymisation can foster responsible data governance engendering trust in security, privacy and data protection that involves data intermediation services.

Especially within the context of the DGA, the role of the DISP could encompass the monitoring of the execution of the agreement between the data holder and data user in question, shaping its legal liability and ethical responsibility depending on the scenario at stake.

Given the growing impact of data on society and the regulatory action aimed at fostering a European data economy, the EU legislator stresses the importance of increased accountability, thereby moving from data management¹¹⁵ towards "responsible data management".¹¹⁶

¹⁰⁶ Carovano and Finck (n 86).

¹⁰⁷ Data Access Agreements features may be recalled in the following examples: EU-Stands4pm: DATA ACCESS [accessed 19.12.2025]; Policy Documentation - EGA European Genome-Phenome Archive [accessed 19.12.2025]; TRE Data access agreement template [accessed 19.12.2025]. The health sector is the one with the vast majority of use cases relying on Data Access Agreement.

¹⁰⁸ Data Use Agreements features may be recalled in the following example: Terms and policies - EBRAINS [accessed 19.12.2025].

¹⁰⁹ Data Sharing Agreement features may be recalled in the following example: Data Sharing Agreement: What You Should Know as a Business [accessed 19.12.2025].

¹¹⁰ Data Transfer Agreement feature may be recalled in the following example: Data Transfer Agreement - EU English [accessed 19.12.2025]. The use of a specific lexicon, namely "transfer" leads to consider this kind of agreement especially in cases of data transfers to third countries outside Europe.

¹¹¹ Among several initiatives: <https://ico.org.uk/media/1061/anonymisation-code.pdf>; Rulebook for a fair data economy (French edition) - Sitra; Data sharing decision form template | ICO [accessed 19.12.2025].

¹¹² Marcel Fassnacht and others, 'Data Sharing Practices: The Interplay of Data, Organizational Structures, and Network Dynamics' (2024) 34 Electronic Markets 47.

¹¹³ In this regard, see extensively: <https://contractsfordatacollaboration.org/our-framework/> [accessed 19.12.2025].

¹¹⁴ The "Contractual Wheel of Data Collaboration" divides the clauses into six categories, namely "why, what, who, how, when and where": <https://contractsfordatacollaboration.org/our-framework/> [accessed 19.12.2025].

¹¹⁵ E Michael Power and Roland L Trope, 'The 2006 Survey of Legal Developments in Data Management, Privacy, and Information Security: The Continuing Evolution of Data Governance' (2006) 62 The Business Lawyer 251 <<https://www.jstor.org/stable/40688420>> accessed 3 April 2024.

¹¹⁶ Julia Stoyanovich, Bill Howe and HV Jagadish, 'Responsible Data Management' (2020) 13 Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment 3474.

In fact, responsible data management is part of “responsible data governance”¹¹⁷ as a cross-functional effort on data management beyond the organisational boundaries of the entity that collects data in the first place. To this extent, data management operations can be subject to audits for legal compliance, as well as to transparency duties when public entities are involved in data collection, data processing, and data release operations, given that contractual arrangements are tied to data management operations.

The DGA fosters the creation of a new business model where the DISPs are required to act as trusted *neutral* third parties, establishing a legal and technical environment to share and access data. These features, crystallised in the DGA, promote more responsible data sharing whose reliability may depend on the accountability of the DISP and its mediation in balancing interests among data holders and data users. In this scenario, where mediated transactions (for sharing and accessing data) take place, clear and strict allocation of roles and legal responsibilities - as well as ethical liabilities - among the parties, may increase the accountability of this legal-technical ecosystem.¹¹⁸ Such accountability can be strengthened by relying on *legal means*, and namely on contractual arrangements whose enforcement and execution are backed by the DISP operating as a *third neutral party*.¹¹⁹ This will allow the DISP, not only to monitor and audit the enforcement and execution of the contractual clauses but at the same time, to uphold legal liability and ethical responsibility for such enforcement and execution, by (active or passive) involvement in data transactions (depending on the shape of its functions and assignments in the given socio-legal-technical ecosystem).¹²⁰

5. Conclusions and further research directions

This article sustains that the DGA has the potential to reduce legal uncertainty to data anonymisation, instilling new confidence in the use of this data processing operation through DISPs. The reconstruction of the legal regime and the European jurisprudence applicable to data anonymisation has shown the main criticalities in the re-identification test on processed data that could have justified the novelties proposed in the Digital Omnibus. Despite the lack of a prescriptive regulatory

approach on anonymisation, at the moment, the DGA seems to be the only one regulatory framework offering a new legal guise for anonymisation as an access gate for further reuses of data in data-driven scenarios.

As the analysis shows, the article contributed to pinpointing the DGA-specific legal provisions that may assist DISPs in the chain of data processing. Contractual arrangements and contractual clauses may represent a central tool for increasing accountability and transparency in data anonymisation when sharing data, as well as in case of accessing a secure processing environment whose control and monitoring activities are exerted by the DISP, as a third neutral party mediating data transactions between data holders and data reusers.

The article shows that the DGA foresees a multi-use and multi-party ecosystem where the reliance on contractual mechanisms will ensure that a neutral and independent governance body, like the DISP, will uphold legal liability and ethical responsibility in granting security, privacy, and data protection. Consequently, DISP may gain momentum as a trustful party for security, privacy, and data protection in data access and data sharing, being not solely accountable for engineering new solutions aimed at unleashing data uses across organisational boundaries, but also legally liable and ethically responsible for it. In this last regard, computational law approaches may need to be further explored to determine how to integrate security and privacy clauses that regulate anonymisation on contractual arrangements meant to (electronically) mediate data sharing or data access between data holders and data reusers, especially within the setting of computable contracts.¹²¹

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

¹¹⁷ Micheli and others (n 73).

¹¹⁸ Heleen Janssen and Jatinder Singh, ‘Data Intermediary’ (2022) 11 Internet Policy Review; Julia Schweihoff and others, ‘Stuck in the Middle with You: Conceptualizing Data Intermediaries and Data Intermediation Services’ (2024) 34 Electronic Markets 48 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-024-00729-9>> accessed 2 October 2024.

¹¹⁹ Podda, ‘Data Governance and Neutral Data Intermediation’ (n 62).

¹²⁰ For instance, the Gaia X ecosystem and its Gaia-X Federation Services (GXFS) encompass the Gaia-X Data Contract Service (GX-DCS) as a broker of data delivery contracts between Data Providers and Data Consumers, mirroring the notary activity as envisaged in the real world. In this regard: Data Contract Service - GXFS.eu [accessed 19.12.2025]. Within the Gaia X ecosystem that takes into account the scenario envisaged by the DGA, data anonymisation may be discussed in their so-called “Data Contract Service” to prevent a potential re-identification of the exchanged anonymised data, and to define (or at least indicate) contractual penalties for such violations. The Data Contract Service may represent the first interface for planning a data exchange between the data provider and the data re-user, providing log tokens to authorize metadata logging while the transaction of data is included in a separate Data Contract.

¹²¹ Harry Surden, ‘Computable Contracts’ (2012) 46 U.C. Davis Law Review 629.